

Gender

Inclusive Business Analysis Module

June 2023

idh
transforming markets

About

Developed by IDH

<https://www.idhsustainabletrade.com/>

Licensed under Creative Commons 4.0 Attribution

You are free to share or adapt the material provided you give attribution to IDH. See the licence information for additional conditions.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

To ensure you are referencing the latest version, please visit the FarmFit Insight Hub

<https://farmfitinsightshub.org/resources> or the IDH Community on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/idh>

Disclaimer

Although every effort has been made to ensure that the content of this publication is up-to-date and accurate, errors and omissions may occur. The information is provided on an “as is” basis and is not intended as a substitute for the reader’s own due diligence and inquiry. IDH does not guarantee or warrant that the information is complete or free of error and accepts no liability for any damage whatsoever arising from any decision or action taken or refrained from in reliance thereon, nor for any inadvertent misrepresentation made or implied.

In this deck

This document includes the theory, guidelines and tools for you to apply the gender module within an Inclusive Business analysis. It assumes you are familiar with the broader methodology, including the Learning Framework, Indicators and Inclusive Business Analysis Financial Model and Case Report. This deck covers below building blocks:

1 Objectives and Learning Questions

Why this module and what do we want to learn about gender in relation to business model performance?

2 Key concepts

What are the bare minimum concepts you need to understand and apply on the intersection of gender and business?

3 Case Report

How do we report on our gender assessment and provide actionable recommendations?

4 Qualitative Assessment

What questions do we ask to assess and score the business model's performance on gender

5 Indicators

What are the gender-related data points we must collect on every business model to answer our learning questions?

6 Definitions and resources

What definitions and theories are underpinning this module?

01

Objectives & Learning Questions

How to conduct the gender module?

Objectives

By applying the gender module as part of the Inclusive Business analysis, we seek to:

1

Generate practical models and concrete guidance for stakeholders in the rural economy on how to better reach and serve rural women with business-driven solutions

2

Articulate the business case for companies to focus on increasing income and (climate) resilience for rural women through improved access to resources

3

Accelerate the adoption and scale of business models that improve rural women's income and resilience, particularly to the stresses and shocks of climate change

ABERA learning questions

The gender module is designed to generate qualitative and quantitative evidence to answer below four overarching questions

Value for rural women

1. How do **financial and agricultural services** integrating climate and gender create value for key profiles of rural women?

Value for businesses

2. How do approaches integrating climate and gender in **strategy and operations** create value for financial and agricultural service providers?

3. Which **key factors in the enabling environment** limit or facilitate investments in inclusive, climate smart business models?

Outcome measurement

4. What are the fewest, easiest to collect, and most **meaningful indicators** to measure and track progress toward FSP business, gender, and climate outcomes?

Farmfit learning questions and hypotheses

Below learning questions and hypotheses are embedded in the Farmfit Learning Framework

Driver	Question/Hypothesis
Land Size & Consolidation	HYP_5: Gender inequalities in land ownership reduce women's access to SDM services
	SRQ_3: How do different SDM operators adjust services to account for differences in land ownership among their farmers?
Household & Off-Farm Activity	HYP_11: Increased female decision-making at farm and/or household level leads to higher productivity levels
	HYP_12: SDMs with smaller gender productivity gaps in their value-chains perform have a higher return on investment
	SRQ_11: To what extent do intra-household gender dynamics have an impact on farming outcomes?
	SRQ_12: How does farming performance differ between female-operated farms and male-operated farms?
	SRQ_13: How does farming performance differ between female-operated farms in male-headed households, and female-operated farms in female-headed households
Financial Service Offering	SRQ_18: What are effective strategies/innovations in improving women's access to financial products?
	HYP_15: SDMs that establish direct payment systems to women to increase their incentive to invest in their agricultural production, this will increase productivity over time
Post-Harvest Service Offering	SRQ_33: What is the difference between female and male operated farms in reported post-harvest losses and how can differences be explained?
Training & Information Service Offering	HYP_28: Gender tailored service provision can help increase women's attendance at training
	SRQ_37: What are effective strategies to increase women's attendance at training?
Equipment & Labour Service Offering	HYP_31: SDMs that offer mechanisation are more successful in reaching female farmers
Farmer Management	SRQ_56: To what extent and how can gender tailored service provision improve production/income?
	HYP_43: Female farmers are more likely to remain in an SDM; therefore, SDMs that target female farmers have higher rates of farmer retention and are more scalable
Farmer Organizations	SRQ_63: How does the creation and support of women's farmer groups translate into reducing gender gaps?
	HYP_62: Female representation in the management of farmer producer organizations can improve the management and efficacy of these organisations
	SRQ_66: What are successful strategies to ensure inclusion of female farmers in FOs?
People, Processes & Governance	SRQ_68: How can gender equality in the SDM's workplace improve SDMs profitability?

02

**Key
Concepts**

Gender lens spectrum

The gender lens spectrum shows a continuum on which a company can be positioned towards becoming more inclusive 'transformative'.

Background: 2X Challenge
 The 2X Challenge is a globally recognised *minimum threshold* for businesses and investments with a gender lens. It was established by the development banks of the G7 with the purpose of earmarking more funding for investments with a gender lens. Since establishment in 2018, multiple investors have joined, and by 2022 the Challenge was set to have raised \$15 billion.

Enablers for inclusion

Ten enablers that are necessary for both men and women to be fully integrated in agricultural value chains

Productivity and market linkages				
<p>1. Inputs Improved seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, livestock vaccines, and labor (household and hired)</p>	<p>2. Assets Land, livestock, and equipment (processing and production)</p>	<p>3. Skills Knowledge of agronomic best practices, literacy, use of tech. and equipment, and business skills</p>	<p>4. Finance Savings/ credit to purchase inputs/ training, access networks, and transport to market</p>	<p>5. Time Adequate time available to perform productive activities (e.g., planning, production, processing, participation in extension, travel)</p>
<p>6. Market Intelligence Information on what to produce at what volume, quality, price and where to sell.</p>	<p>7. Mobility Ability to access public spaces (both physically and socially) to enable transport of goods to market and access services and training</p>	<p>8. Buyer Linkages Availability of secure connection to buyers of agricultural products</p>		
<p>9. Business, policy and legal environment Existence of supportive and non-discriminatory environment to foster business growth (regulations, investment), policies that support enablers of the agricultural value chain (input subsidy programs, rural infrastructure development), and laws that govern allocation of resources (land titling and inheritance laws)</p>			<p>10. Infrastructure Roads and freight infrastructure; electricity, irrigation; post-harvest storage infrastructure</p>	

03

Case Report

Case Report

This section includes the key analysis performed on gender as reported on in the Inclusive Business Case Report.

Analysis	Purpose
Recommendations	Provides actionable recommendations for the company on how to close/diminish any existing gaps for each of the five assessed business areas, based on the scoring and other observations in each of these areas.
Gender intentionality assessment	Shows the outcome of the gender assessment per business area and the overall classification on the gender spectrum. It also allows you to highlight the main outcomes/remarks/observations (be it positive or negative) per business area as well as on the overall assessment.
Gender innovation business case	<p>Allows you to dive a bit deeper into a specific, innovative, gender-related aspect of the business model, both qualitatively and quantitatively.</p> <p>On the left you show a schematic representation of the specific aspect. On the right you can elaborate further and quantify the business case for both the company as well as the women (given that sufficient data is available)</p>
Gender context scan	This slide shows some macro-level indicators of gender equality and risks for the country of interest and compares them to those same indicators at a company level (given that data is available).
Gender as part of organogram	The main goal of this slide is to get a better understanding of the organization and its strengths and weaknesses, but it also sheds some light on the gender balance within the organization, which can provide valuable input when formulating gender-related recommendations.

Recommendations

We have identified and prioritised recommendations that [company] can explore across the highlighted opportunity pathways:

Theme	Recommended next steps	Priority	Effort	Timeline
Gender	Gender intentionality: [company] should develop an explicit gender strategy, which should be documented and actively communicated externally			<1 year
	Workplace policies and practices: [company] would benefit from developing workplace policies, e.g., paid maternity leave beyond the nationally required minimum, or on-site childcare facilities			1-3 years
	Overall: To assess their impact, [company] should take steps to measure outcomes to know if approaches lead to gender transformation in specific business areas. Outcomes should measure if there has been a reduced gender gap or changed gender norm			<1 year

High

Medium

Low

Gender context scan

This slide captures contextual challenges and opportunities related to gender. The ratios that are shown can be changed based on relevance and availability of data. Some ratios only apply to the country as a whole, for others you can show how the company performs compared to the country average.

Input for this slide is 1) the enabling environment survey, 2) desk research ([see this slide](#)), possibly 3) PDC if available and 4) anecdotal evidence from the company interview.

Ratio	[Country]	[Company name]	Observations
Primary education enrolment	0.90		Aaa
Estimated earned income	0.78		Aaa
Bank account ownership	0.65		Aaa
Financial inclusion	0.74		Aaa
Employee gender ratio	0.94	0.28	Aaa
Women in leadership	0.42	0.50	Aaa
Average yield	0.90	0.85	Aaa
Equal pay	0.56	1.00	Aaa

Gender assessment

Observations

There is no explicit gender strategy

There is a limited number of workplace policies

Aaa

Aaa

Gender innovation

[company] sets up women groups and VSLAs, and trains them in parboiling. The groups parboil rice for [company] a share of the profits in the VSLA

The relevance and content of this slide very much depends on a case-to-case basis. When discussing gender with the company, always be on the lookout for gender innovations. Think of things like:

- Women groups, VSLAs, coops
- Female-led farm segments
- Women-heavy value chains
- Women tailored service
- Financial inclusion

[company] bu

- Initial investments in training and equipment of \$xxx are required for each group
- However, it does allow [company] to acquire additional volumes of high moisture rice, which allows them to tap into high value markets and **increase their profits from \$xxx/MT to \$xx/MT**
- This means that [company] will have earned back their investment after sourcing just **x MT** from a group

Women's business case

- Women earn on average **xxx xxx per week** with the current capacity of xx bags per person. With experience this could be increased to xx, thereby increasing profits
- By making weekly contributions to the group VSLA, it also provides the women with **access to small-scale loans**
- The extra income and access to finance increase the women's control over financial resources, and thereby their **(financial) independence**

Organizational structure

- **Gender ratio:** At the senior management level, only x out of x (xx%) is female. In the entire company, only x out of x (x%) is female
- **Agents:** [Company name] currently employs x extension officers, that are each overseeing x farmers. With their plans to increase the number of farmers from x to x, the agent to farmer ratio will change from x to x

Male	Female
Multiple	Vacant

Context scan: macro-level data on gender risks

This section provides guidance to assess the macro-level dimensions of gender risks that can be compared against data from the company along with resources for research. See the context slide above

Indicator for comparison	Rationale	Databases
Labor force participation	Reflects social, legal, and cultural trends and norms that determine women's access to economic activities	<p>Labour force participation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> World Economic Forum - Global Gender Gap Report . Download the latest report and find the indicator under <i>Economic Participation and opportunity</i>. World Bank Data - female indicator and male indicator. <p>Estimated earned income:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> World Economic Forum - Global Gender Gap Report. Download the latest report and find the indicator under <i>Economic Participation and opportunity</i>. <p>Agricultural land ownership:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> FAO's Gender and Lands Rights Database. Look for "Incidence of female/male agricultural landowners" indicator. <p>Value chain average yield:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> FAO's crop database. Select the <i>Country</i>, under "<i>Elements</i>" select "<i>Yield</i>" and under "<i>Item</i>" select "<i>Crop</i>" then select the <i>year</i> under review. Click "<i>Download data</i>" <p>Education enrolment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> World Bank Data - female indicator and male indicator World Economic Forum - Global Gender Gap Report . Download the latest report and find the indicator under <i>Education Attainment</i> <p>Women in leadership:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> DHS Program – Look for the most recent DHS report of the country <p>Financial inclusion:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Global Findex Database – Download the data to find this indicator for the country
Estimated earned income	Indicates gender differences in the ability to capture value from participation in economic activities	
Agricultural land ownership	Women's land rights are fundamental for the realization of food security and increased agricultural productivity	
Value chain average yield	Understanding the national average yield, and then comparing it to company gender disaggregated data will shed light on yield opportunities for the business	
Education enrolment	Educated women can seek and use information for the betterment of the health, nutrition and education of their households, and are also empowered to play a meaningful role at their households	
Women in leadership	Indicates women's empowerment as far as participating in decision making is concerned	
Financial inclusion	Benefits from financing inclusion can be wide ranging for women farmers: digital financial services can help farmers manage financial risk, increase savings, reduce overall travel/wait time to obtain/make payments etc.	

04

Qualitative Assessment

Design of qualitative assessment

The assessment builds on existing frameworks and outputs standard indicators and scores

1 Frameworks

- Non-standard assessments
- Different needs of assessors
- Particular needs of assessed companies

2 Indicators

- Mostly qualitative in nature
- Some are objective and simple
- Others are subjective and complex

3 Scoring

- By-indicator: binary/ternary assessment
- From qualitative to quantitative – percentages

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Who does the assessment?

Analyst or enumerator conducting a country visit to the assessed company. Must be a person **trained for the purpose**.

How to do the assessment?

1. The analyst should complete the assessment **progressively during the various sessions** with the company (i.e., not a single sitting)
2. The analyst asks for the information, **one indicator at the time**. The provided 'suggested guiding questions' can be used for the purpose
3. Some indicators need **elaborate information** prior to be assessed. When this is the case, **prompts are suggested** (e.g., how, in which ways...?)
4. Based on the collected answers, the analyst **assesses each indicator** (YES/NO, or HIGH/MEDIUM/LOW)
5. The **final score** (percentage) is **calculated automatically**

When to conduct the gender interview

This shows a sample timeline of an Inclusive Business analysis. It is advised to populate the scoring tool as you discuss scoping, kick-off and strategy on an ad-hoc basis. Then, have a dedicated gender interview (1.5 hours) latest during the site visit. Ask only those questions that have not been answered yet

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Section 1. Intentionality

- Does your company offer services specifically tailored to women farmers?
- Does your staff have an understanding of the differences in how men and women among your farmers access resources and services differently?
 - If yes, How?
- Does your company have gender equality as a strategic goal that is communicated in documents (e.g., in vision, mission, strategic plan)?
- Does your company allocate resources -- financial or human capital -- towards executing your gender strategy?
- Does your company track gender-related KPIs?
- Does your company have targets for reaching women farmers?
- Does your company have an in-house gender expert or gender advisor to support training and provide gender expertise on business activities?

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Section 2. Workplace policies and practices

- Does your company collect employees' gender-disaggregated data?
- "Does your company generate internal insights with the employees' gender-disaggregated data that is collected?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- "Does your company tailor its business strategy based on the insights from employees' gender-disaggregated data?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- "Does your company take actions based on the insights from employees' gender-disaggregated data?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- Among the staff in your company, what percentage are women?
- Among the staff in your company, what percentage are under 30 years old?
- Among the staff in your company, what percentage are over 50 years old?
- Among the senior and middle managers in your company, what percentage are women?
- Among the senior and middle managers in your company, what percentage are under 30 years old?
- Among the senior and middle managers in your company, what percentage are over 50 years old?
- Does your company have an equal pay for equal work policy?
- Does your company have an anti-sexual harassment and violence policy?
- Does your company have procedures that allow victims of violence or harassment at work to report it without fear of reprisal (e.g., trusted advisor, appointed member of staff, emergency hotlines)?
- "Does your company monitor the application of these inclusive workplace policies and procedures?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- "Does your company take actions based on monitored data of the application of inclusive workplace policies and procedures?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Section 3. Farmer engagement (1/2)

- Do the women-tailored services that your company offers allow women farmers to have more empowerment?
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How? (e.g., -Women leadership trainings, -Joint household decision making sessions, etc.)"
- Does your company identify each of the farmers through unique contract / ID / account number?
- Does your company collect farmers' gender-disaggregated data?
- "Does your company generate internal insights with the farmers' gender-disaggregated data?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- "Does your company tailor its business strategy based on the insights from farmers' gender-disaggregated data?"
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, How?"
- While developing new products and services, does your company consult men and women farmer separately to understand their differences in needs, behavior, and preferences?
- Does your company tailor products and services for women farmers according to their unique needs (e.g., different input package sizes, crop lifecycle/harvest, cash flow availability, literacy/skills constraints, social norms around mobility)?
- Does your company tailor the marketing and delivery of services considering women farmers' unique needs and preferences (e.g., digital vs. physical 'location', time and location of meeting, literacy levels)?

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Section 3. Farmer engagement (2/2)

- Among the farmer base of your company, what percentage are women?
- Among the farmer base of your company, What percentage are under 30 years old?
- Among the farmer base of your company, What percentage are over 50 years old?
- Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are women?
- Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are under 30 years old?
- Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are over 50 years old?
- Does your company review other requirements than a payment fee (e.g., owning land titles, entering into contracts, putting forward collateral) to ensure that they enable access by both women and men?"
- Does your company offer adequate feedback channels available to women farmers according to their unique needs (e.g., digital vs. physical, literacy levels, social norms, etc.)?
 - -Proposed Prompt: If yes, which ones?
- Does your company solicit feedback or input from women farmers regarding your company's services?
- Does your company take actions based on the feedback provided by women farmers?
- Do women and men farmers demonstrate comparable benefits from your company's services (e.g., productivity gains, income gains)?

Scoring Tool

Below is a screenshot of the Excel scoring tool that provides all questions and guidance for the analyst to assess the company and get to the final scoring. Scores can then be translated to the respective analysis in the Case Report

	A	B	C	F	G	H	J	K	
1	Section	Indicator	Suggested guiding question		Scoring criteria	Assigned score	Partial score	Quant. Score (section)	
32	Farmer engagement	are women:		LOW	percentage ≤ 25%				
		Farmers' percentage of women under 30 years old	Among the farmer base of your company, What percentage are under 30 years old?	HIGH	percentage ≈ 50%				
33				MEDIUM	25% < percentage < 50%	HIGH	2.44%	100%	
				LOW	percentage ≤ 25%				
34		Farmers' percentage of women above 50 years old	Among the farmer base of your company, What percentage are over 50 years old?	HIGH	percentage ≈ 50%				
				MEDIUM	25% < percentage < 50%	HIGH	2.44%		
35		Farmer with leadership roles' percentage of women	Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are women?	LOW	percentage ≤ 25%				
				HIGH	percentage ≈ 50%				
36		Farmer with leadership roles' percentage of women under 30 years old	Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are under 30 years old?	MEDIUM	25% < percentage < 50%	HIGH	2.44%		
				LOW	percentage ≤ 25%				
37	Farmer with leadership roles' percentage of women above 50 years old	Among the farmers of your farmer base with leadership roles, what percentage are over 50 years old?	HIGH	percentage ≈ 50%					
			MEDIUM	25% < percentage < 50%	HIGH	2.44%			
			LOW	percentage ≤ 25%					
		Revision of services' requirements (other than payment) to enable access to both women and men	[This question is not to be scored] Do the farmers of your company must meet other requirements than a payment fee to access your company's services? -Proposed Prompt: If yes, which ones? (e.g., owning land titles, entering into contracts, putting forward collateral)	YES	Company revises services' requirements to enable access	YES	2.44%		
			[If previous question is answered as 'Yes'] Does your company review these other requirements than a payment fee to ensure that they enable access by both women and men?	NO	Company does not revise services' requirements to enable access				
38		Feedback channels to women farmers according to their needs	Does your company offer adequate feedback channels available to women farmers according to their unique needs (e.g., digital vs. physical, literacy levels, social norms, etc.)? -Proposed Prompt: If yes, which ones?	YES	Company has feedback channels suited to women farmers	YES	2.44%		
				NO	Company does not have feedback channels suited to women farmers				
39		Feedback on services solicited to women farmers	Does your company solicit feedback or input from women farmers regarding your company's services?	YES	Company solicits feedback from women farmers	YES	2.44%		
				NO	Company does not solicit feedback from women farmers				
40		Taking of actions based on feedback of women farmers	Does your company take actions based on the feedback provided by women farmers?	YES	Company takes actions based on the feedback	YES	2.44%		
				NO	Company does not take actions based on the feedback				
41		Women and men farmers demonstrate comparable benefits from accessing the company's services	Do women and men farmers demonstrate comparable benefits from your company's services (e.g., productivity gains, income gains)?	YES	Women and men farmers demonstrate benefits (backed with evidence/data)	YES	2.44%		
				NO	Women and men farmers don't demonstrate benefit (or no data at all)				
42	OVERALL SCORE							100%	
43									

05

Indicators

Indicators

This section mentions all indicators that are captured as part of the Inclusive Business analysis. Indicators are captured on different dimensions and stored in different tools

Dimension	Data collection	Data storage
Gender intentionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company interview on gender (see interview guidelines) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scores + full answers in Scoring Tool Total and sub-scores in Indicator tab (Financial Model)
Gender context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desk research (see resources) Company interview on gender Enabling Environment survey (see resources) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context-specific indicators in Indicator tab Enabling Environment on Monday.com and Indicator tab (Financial Model)
Gender innovation business case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company interviews on business model Company and farmer P&L data request (see below) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not stored in comparable way at innovation-level, only on company- and farmer-level
Company business case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company P&L data request (Excel) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not stored in a gender-disaggregated way
Farmer business case (only if farmers are segmented based on gender)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmer P&L data request (Excel) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only stored in a gender-disaggregated way when segmented based on gender <i>If stored:</i> Indicator tab (Financial Model)
Farming household (optional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary data collection (farmer survey through AKVO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data delivery file (excel) Farmfit Intelligence Portal

Indicators: gender

This is a long-list of gender related indicators collected as part of the Inclusive Business analysis

#	Indicator	Unit	Source	Definition
D1.01	SDM operator position on Gender Graduation Ladder	Select	SDM Analysis	Indicator that measures how intentional is the SDM operator about gender
D1.02	Share of female farmers	%	SDM Analysis	Share of females served over the duration of the SDM
D1.03	Primary education enrollment	Ratio	External data	Ratio of men to women enrolled in primary education
D1.04	Women in decision making	%	External data	Percentage of married women who participate in decision-making
D1.17	Women's undertaking of reproductive activities, SDM	%	PDC only	Percentage of females carrying out significant level of reproductive activities
D1.18	Women's undertaking of productive activities, SDM	%	PDC only	Percentage of females carrying out significant level of productive activities
D1.05	Women using a bank account or mobile money service	%	External data	Percentage of women who have a bank account or used a mobile money service in the past year
D1.06	Women in leadership positions	Ratio	SDM Analysis	Ratio of men to women covering leadership positions in the SDM
D1.07	Women labor force participation	Ratio	External data	Ratio of men to women participation to labor force
D1.08	Women employee ratio	Ratio	SDM Analysis	Ratio of men to women as employees of the SDM operator
D1.09	Percentage of female farmers (crop specific)	%	SDM Analysis	National percentage of female farmers cultivating the crop analysed in the SDM
D1.19	Female farmer percentage of those receiving financial services	%	SDM Analysis	Percentage of those receiving financial services who are female farmers, within the SDM
D1.11	Female ratio of income, national	Ratio	External data	Ratio of the national income of men to women
D1.15	Gender tailored service provision	Yes/No	SDM Analysis	Whether the SDM operator offers different services to women and men.
D1.16	Services aimed at gender equality	Yes/No	SDM Analysis	Whether the SDM operator offers services that target gender equality (e.g. women leadership course, sexual harrasments programs etc)
D1.20	Gender tailored payments	Yes/No	SDM Analysis	Does the SDM take account of gender in the way that it makes payments (cash or in form of inputs) to farmers
D1.21	Gender disaggregated data collection	Yes/No	SDM Analysis	Does the SDM operator collect data on farming households disaggregated by gender
D1.22	Average length of farmer relationship, female	#	PDC only	Average length of time that SDM maintains a relationship with its female farm operators
D1.23	Average length of farmer relationship, male	#	PDC only	Average length of time that SDM maintains a relationship with its male farm operators
D1.24	Average hours of unpaid labour female operated farm	#	PDC only	Average hours of unpaid labour per day undertaken by female farm operators
D1.25	Average hours of unpaid labour male operated farm	#	PDC only	Average hours of unpaid labour per day undertaken by male farm operators
D1.26	Receipt of Training and Information services female operated farms	%	PDC only	% of female operated farms in receipt of Training and Information services in last 12 months
D1.27	Receipt of Training and Information services male operated farms	%	PDC only	% of male operated farms in receipt of Training and Information services in last 12 months
D1.28	Receipt of input services female operated farms	%	PDC only	% of female operated farms in receipt of input services in last 12 months
D1.29	Receipt of input services male operated farms	%	PDC only	% of male operated farms in receipt of input services in last 12 months
D1.30	Receipt of finance services female operated farms	%	PDC only	% of female operated farms in receipt of finance services in last 12 months
D1.31	Receipt of finance services male operated farms	%	PDC only	% of male operated farms in receipt of finance services in last 12 months
D1.32	Women's farmer groups	Yes/No	SDM Analysis	The presence of women's farmer groups in the value-chain
D1.33	Land ownership female operated farms	%	PDC only	% of female operated farms owning the land
D1.34	Land ownership male operated farms	%	PDC only	% of male operated farms owning the land
D1.35	Women's decision-making productive activities, SDM farmers	%	PDC only	% of decisions for productive activities made either by female alone or joint with partner/another household member

Indicators: climate

This is a long-list of gender related indicators collected as part of the Inclusive Business analysis

	Climate resilience lens	Unit	Source	Definition
D3.01.1	Environmental risks - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.2	Environmental risks - Flooding	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.3	Environmental risks - Heavy rainfall patterns	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.4	Environmental risks - High temperature or droughts	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.5	Environmental risks - Pests and disease	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.6	Environmental risks - Windstorms	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.7	Environmental risks - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.1	Farm management risks - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.2	Farm management risks - Damaging pesticide	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.3	Farm management risks - Monoculture practices	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.4	Farm management risks - Over-fertilization	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.5	Farm management risks - Over-irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.6	Farm management risks - Suboptimal crop variety	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.7	Farm management risks - Under-fertilization	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.8	Farm management risks - Under-irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.9	Farm management risks - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.03.1	Environmental services - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.2	Environmental services - Agroforestry or diversification	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.3	Environmental services - Improved crop varieties	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.4	Environmental services - Insurance	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.5	Environmental services - Integral pest management	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.6	Environmental services - Smart irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.7	Environmental services - Sustainable input provision	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.8	Environmental services - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.04	Climate resilience Go to index	#	External data	This Go to index summarizes a country's vulnerability (exposure and sensitivity) and readiness (ability to leverage investments and convert them to adaptation actions) to the negative impact of climate change
D3.05	Soil degradation	Qualitative range	External data	This indicator shows the severity of soil degradation in 4 categories: water, wind, physical and chemical deterioration.
D3.06	Water risk	Qualitative range	External data	This indicator identifies areas with water-related risks, based on 12 subcategories such as drought severity, seasonal variability and ground water stress
D3.07	Human footprint	#	External data	The human footprint map measures the cumulative impact of direct pressures on nature from human activities. It includes eight inputs such as buildings, crop land and population density.

06

Definitions & Resources

Definitions

Term	Definition
Gender Transformative Business Model (GTBM)	“A GTBM is a model that goes beyond looking at sex-disaggregated data. It goes beyond seeing gender as women and looks at root causes of gender equality. It means that, a business has to think about the context that they are embedded in. Their context informs the success of their own business model. So, addressing the enabling environment and norms that environment is what would contribute to GTBM.”
Placeholder	test
Placeholder	test

Key resources

Name	Author(s)	Accessibility	Purpose
Value for Women final report	Value for Women	Private	Test
IDH Gender Toolkit	Dalberg	Private	Test
<u>AgriFin Gender transformative toolkit</u>	MercyCorps	Public	Test
ABERA pitch deck may 2023	CGAP, IDH	Public	test
Farmfit Learning & Innovation Framework v2.2	IDH	Private	Test
<u>Global Gender Gap Report</u>	World Economic Forum	Public	The Global Gender Gap Index annually benchmarks the current state and evolution of gender parity across four key dimensions (Economic Participation and Opportunity, Educational Attainment, Health and Survival, and Political Empowerment).
<u>Demographic and Health Survey</u>	DHS Program	Public	The Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) Program has collected, analyzed, and disseminated accurate and representative data on population, health, HIV, and nutrition through more than 400 surveys in over 90 countries.

07

Annex

IDH Inclusive Business Analysis

offers practical, data-informed insights to **innovate, build and scale** business models towards resilient viable, inclusive value chains.

Scope and study approach

- The Inclusive Business analysis is a business model analysis focusing on the interaction between company and smallholder farmer business case
- Builds on both industry-standard, and tailor-made frameworks and tools: e.g., Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder), P&L, Digital Maturity assessment (KPMG)
- Aggregates wide range of contextual, operational, financial, and agroeconomic data, both qualitative and quantitative
- **Goes broad and deep:** combines cross-sectional data collection with a case study approach*

**A cross-sectional study is a type of research design in which you collect data from many different individuals at a single point in time
A case study is used to generate an in-depth, multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue in its real-life context*

Modularity

Modularity is a design principle that subdivides a product into smaller parts called modules, which can be independently created, modified, replaced, or exchanged with other modules or between different systems.

Due to its modularity the Inclusive Business analysis can:

- Assess a wide range of different companies, value chains and sustainability issues
- Provide insights to different audiences: program and investment managers
- Generate in-depth case study and aggregate benchmarking insights

Modules

We currently have 13 content modules within three categories (greyed out are still to be finalized)

